

SAINT: SIMPLE STATIC TAINT ANALYSIS TOOL

User's manual

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August 30, 2015

Contents

1	Author's Biography	2
2	Introduction	3
3	Installation Instructions	3
3.1	Required Software	3
3.2	Environment Variables	3
4	How to Configure "clang+llvm" for use with SAINT	4
5	How to Configure "LLVM" for use with SAINT	4
6	Folder Structure	5
7	How to Compile and Run SAINT	5
7.1	Configuration Files	5
7.2	How to Run SAINT	6
7.3	How to Get Debug Messages from SAINT	6

1 Author's Biography

Figure 1: The author Xavier NOUMBISSI NOUNDOU

Xavier NOUMBISSI NOUNDOU is from CAMEROON and holds the title Diplom-Informatiker [DIPL.-INF.] ¹ (roughly equivalent to a canadian Master's degree in Computer Science) of the **University of Bremen** ² in Germany.

After his Diplom-Informatiker degree, he worked 21 months (November 2007 – July 2009) as Software Developer for **Siemens Healthcare** ³ in Erlangen (Germany).

After **Siemens**, Xavier started his doctoral research in Program Analysis and Software Engineering in the **Watform Lab** at the **University of Waterloo** ⁴ (Waterloo, Ontario, Canada).

From January 2012 to August 2012 (8 months), Xavier worked in the Java J9–JIT compilation team of **IBM Toronto Lab.** in Markham (Ontario, Canada) as a graduate intern in compiler optimization.

Xavier is professionally proficient in the French, English and German languages.

For his DIPL.-INF. degree, Xavier worked on the automatic generation of test cases for reactive systems. The algorithms he developed are used by the German company

¹<http://www.inb.uni-luebeck.de/~boehme/diplinf.html>

²<http://www.uni-bremen.de>

³<http://www.healthcare.siemens.com>

⁴<http://www.uwaterloo.ca>

Verified Systems International GmbH⁵. The title of his diplom-informatiker thesis was "Statistical test cases generation for reactive systems".

Xavier currently works on his PhD degree. His research focuses on program analysis and software engineering. He is the creator of **SAINT**⁶, which is a tool to perform static taint analysis on programs written in the C programming language.

2 Introduction

Businesses increasingly use software. This is even more relevant for companies relying on e-commerce. However, software is error-prone and contain several bugs. Security bugs are one of the major problems faced by companies today. In the worst case, security bugs enable unauthorized users to gain full control of an application.

My PhD thesis introduces the concept of *tainted paths* and describes techniques and algorithms to compute them in any imperative programming language that uses pointers (C, C++, Java, etc.). I implemented these algorithms in **SAINT**.

SAINT does not require the developer to annotate the program under analysis. **SAINT** implements a flow-sensitive, interprocedural and context-sensitive analysis that computes tainted paths in C programs at compile-time.

3 Installation Instructions

This section explains how to install **SAINT** on a "Linux" machine. We haven't tested **SAINT** on a "Windows" or "Mac OS" machine, but the installation should follow similar steps.

3.1 Required Software

This section enumerates all software that you need to run **SAINT**.

- **SAINT**: <http://github.com/xnoubissinoundou/yeroth.rd.saint>
- The compiler infrastructure LLVM, version 3.3: <http://llvm.org>
- The DSA pointer analysis poolalloc: <http://github.com/llvm-mirror/poolalloc>

3.2 Environment Variables

Table 1 that shows all environment variables that you have to define and export in order to successfully run **SAINT**.

✓ You define and export an environment variable **ENV_VAR** by writing the following commands in your "\$HOME/.bashrc" file:

⁵<http://www.verified.de>

⁶<https://www.github.com/xaviernoubis/saint>

Environment variables	Description
<code>SAINT_HOME</code>	SAINT home folder (e.g. <code>/home/user/saint</code>)
<code>SAINT_BIN</code>	SAINT binaries folder (e.g. <code>SAINT_HOME/bin</code>)
<code>LLVM_HOME</code>	llvm home folder (e.g. <code>/home/user/llvm</code>)
<code>LLVM_LIB</code>	llvm compiled libraries folder (e.g. <code>LLVM_HOME/build/Release+Asserts/lib</code>)
<code>LLVM_BIN</code>	llvm compiled binaries (e.g. <code>LLVM_HOME/build/Release+Asserts/bin</code>)
<code>POOLALLOC</code>	poolalloc home folder (e.g. <code>/home/user/poolalloc</code>)
<code>CLANGLLVMLIB</code>	clang+llvm binaries' folder (e.g. <code>/home/user/clang-llvm/bin</code>)

Table 1: Table with all environment variables required to install and use SAINT

```
ENV_VAR=path_to_folder
export ENV_VAR
```

4 How to Configure "clang+llvm" for use with SAINT

- a) Download and unpack clang+llvm, version 3.3.
- b) Add the bin folder to your environment variable `PATH`.
 ✓ For instance by adding the following line in your file `"$HOME/.bashrc"`

```
PATH=$PATH:$CLANGLLVMLIB
export PATH
```

5 How to Configure "LLVM" for use with SAINT

- a) Open the file `"$LLVM_HOME/lib/Analysis/Makefile"` and append the string "saint" to the "DIRS" variable. Following is an excerpt of the file.

```
##===- lib/Analysis/Makefile -----*- Makefile -*===##
#
#                               The LLVM Compiler Infrastructure
#
# This file is distributed under the University of Illinois Open Source
# License. See LICENSE.TXT for details.
#
##===-----##
```

```
LEVEL = ../../
LIBRARYNAME = LLVMAnalysis
DIRS = IPA saint
BUILD_ARCHIVE = 1

include $(LEVEL)/Makefile.common
```

b) Run the script `saint-configure.sh`.

6 Folder Structure

The following folders constitute `SAINT`'s directory structure:

1. `bin`: folder with the scripts:
 - `saint-gen-ir.sh`: generates the LLVM IR for code analyzed by `SAINT`.
 - `saint-run-llvm-opt.sh`: runs LLVM (`opt` binary) with `SAINT` as plugin.
 - `saint-configure.sh`: configures and compiles `poolalloc` and LLVM for `SAINT`.
2. `benchmarks`: folder with sample scripts to run `SAINT`.
3. `cfg`: folder with source, sink, and sanitizer configuration files
4. `projects`: folder with sample projects.
5. `doc`: folder with the manual.
6. `src`: folder with all C++ source files, and Bash scripts to compile and run `SAINT`.

7 How to Compile and Run SAINT

✓ You need to execute the command `"make -f Makefile.saint"` within the folder `"$LLVM_HOME/lib/Analysis/saint"` to compile `SAINT`.

Also, `SAINT` gets compiled when you run it using the Bash script `saint-run-llvm-opt.sh`.

7.1 Configuration Files

Configuration files are found in the folder `"$SAINT_HOME/cfg"`. There are three configuration files:

- `sources.cfg`: taint sources configuration file
Each line of the file specifies a function name and an integer `"x"`. `"x"` is the argument of the function that is tainted.
If `"x"` is zero (0), then it is the return value of the function that is tainted.

```
fopen,0  
fgets,1
```

The previous lines specify that `fopen` returns a tainted value, and that `fgets` taints its first argument.

- `sinks.cfg`: taint sinks configuration file
Each line of the file specifies a function name and an integer "y". "y" is the argument of the function that must not received a tainted value. "y" is never equal to zero (0).

```
printf,1
```

The previous line denotes that `printf` must not received a tainted value as its first argument (i.e. `printf` is sensible function).

- `sanitizers.cfg`: sanitizers configuration file
`SAINT` doesn't yet implement this functionality.

7.2 How to Run SAINT

Among others, `SAINT` source folder contains the following two important Bash scripts:

- `saint-gen-ir.sh`: this script is used to generate and merge llvm intermediate representation (IR) files.
- `saint-run-opt.sh`: this script is used to run the analysis of `SAINT` on the program under analysis.

We encourage users to look at the sample scripts in the folders "projects" and "benchmarks" to learn how to use `saint-gen-ir.sh` and `saint-run-opt.sh`.

7.3 How to Get Debug Messages from SAINT